

Aspirations of Students and Social Work Education in North Maharashtra Region

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Abstract :

This research paper is an approach to understand and study aspirations of specialized social work students to work in society. The descriptive research design with quantitative research methodology. The strong argument resulted with the factual data of students social workers in the north Maharashtra region are aspirants for social development to address social issues and resolve problems.

Introduction

The present scenario of Social Work Education and practice is with issues and concern regarding quality at most. The standard curriculum, pedagogy, teaching learning methods and field work practices are under reservation to its standardization. The uniformity is not unanimous in social work education. The complex society with existing social problems is evident to the emergence of new realities in social sciences. The relevance of social work education needed an essence of contemporary world of social realities. The scope of social work profession in India is demanding but the employment opportunities are at stake. Hence this research paper is an effort of the Ph.D. research scholar to explore Student engagement in Social Work Education is the aspiration for Government job rather than a vision of social development.

Rationale and Significance:

The changing context of social work is unrecognized by the governance of academic institutions. It reflected in insignificant visibility of social work profession. Today's era is of qualitative and output driven academics, research and extension. The stakeholders are playing pivotal role in ensuring standardization of social work education. Hence it is needed to understand the aspirations of students.

Statement of Problem:

The five NMU Jalgaon affiliated colleges of social work education and department of social work at university campus are having minimal presence in socio-political discourses to study or intervene in resolving social problems. These institutions are producing sizable number of social work professionals but their work is unable to make remarkable positive mark in society. The professional social worker's role is very important for a visible social change. In this context, on the aftermath of platinum jubilee of social work education in India, it is essential to do an analysis of quality of social work education in North Maharashtra Region.

Objective :

To understand the alumni profile their motives, perceptions and proactive engagement in the field of social development

Hypothesis:

Student engagement in Social Work Education is the aspiration for Government job rather than a vision of social development.

Research Design :

The all social work colleges affiliated to North Maharashtra University will be the universe of study. It covers three districts i.e. Jalgaon, Dhule and Nadurbar. These districts have six social work institutions including a department of Social Work at university campus. Bhagini Mandal's Social Work College, Chopda, Jalgaon; Dhanaji Nana Choudhary Vidya Prabodhini's Social work College, Kusumba, Jalgaon; Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru Social Work College, Amlner, Jalgaon; Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar College of Social Work Education, Morane, Dhule and Mahatma Phule College of Social Work, Taloda, Nadurbar the aforesaid enlisted colleges and Social Work Department of NMU, Jalgaon were the locus of study.

This research study was a combination of qualitative and quantitative investigation. The descriptive cum exploratory research design was adopted for the study. Primary and secondary method of data collection was used. The SPSS is a computerized tool of data analysis used for analysis. The method of sampling was simple random sampling, under that sequential and quota sampling method was adopted. This research paper is based on the sample size of 304 students out of total sample size of 492.

Total Sample size was including 25 student Alumni, 25 students of final year, 25 students of first year, 5 teachers and 2 management personnel i.e. 82 sample from each social work institution. The total sample size was 492 including 25 student alumni of social work department of university campus.

Specialization in Social Work Education

The Tata Institute of Social Sciences has offered five specializations in social work education in year 1953. These specialization called as the "Concentrations". It introduced with a special objective to train trainee social workers in a specialized course. Current trend in social work education have a common similarity of having different specializations. These specializations are like medical and psychiatric social work, Community development, Family and child welfare, Personal management and Industrial training. There are also new trends are set by the premium institutes like Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai. The new specialization as Dalit and tribe centered social work introduced recently. These specializations transformed into the specialized degree courses as M.A. in Dalit and tribe centered social work, M.A. in Community Development etc. These courses are having the common foundation courses in first year. It proposed that instead of offering the old and conventional specialization the center of excellence should offer specialized courses in a particular field. For example, NIMHANS, Bangalore is offering course of social work education with a specialization as in Medical and psychiatric social work.

Social Work Education in Development Paradigm

The critical exploration of innovative emerging models of SWE in Asia was carried out

by Nanavati M.C. The SWE has western philosophy as theoretical premise. Author has suggested ' New Models of Social Work Education '. Profession education has 5 basic components i.e. Context, Purpose, Structure, Content and Process. Co-relation and integration of these components in a process are called as "Curriculum Development". The contemporary scenarios of social, cultural and economic context explore the social work curriculum. Theories of social development and social change are having basic premise in objectives of SWE. The point of contradiction in SWE is related with personal to social development. Egalitarian society is envisioned by professional social workers but the question is in individual or professional growth. Today's industrial civilization has an impact on SWE and practice. The social work profession would intervene in various issues of development paradigm. It can be understood in relation to illiteracy, industrialization, social security and universal employment. These challenges need to be addressed by the application of indigenized knowledge.

Indigenized knowledge considered as a base for resolving the challenges to set alternate model to social work practice. The discourse of indigenization carried forward since its emergence. Unfortunately, its academic and practical applicability could not achieve in India and the third world countries. The causes in failure of indigenization are explained as below

1. Elite middle class intellectuals could not find their roots in the ground reality. These elite intellectuals influenced by the western philosophy.
2. Traditional approach had a fundamentalist identity. On the contrary, liberal perspectives acclaimed and widely accepted. Hence, the role of indigenization has its own limits.
3. The emotional unrest in societies demands an alternate model of social work education where intellectual thoughts combine with emotional urge.
4. The elitist intellectuals and their western conditioning did not promote indigenization. There is a failure in balancing the influence of actual roots and concepts-theories of great masters

Discourse of indigenization is existed generally in social sciences and particularly in sociology, anthropology etc. The national and regional milieus are the basic reasons to increase urge to change and ask for an alternate model. There are three different types on interests in the social workers. These interests influence curriculum designing and development that explained below

First, these people are working in masses to resolve their problems. They have the means of Conscientisation and structural change to deal with social problems. They have very little faith in academic training of social work education. Second, there are the professionals having specialized training in respected fields of interest. The third group of professionals is interested in personal and professional self-development. These interests of professionals considered as to develop the alternate model of social work education in third world countries. These three alternate models are as Model-A-Change Oriented, Model-B-Mixed and Model-C-Professional Interest Based.

Specialized Student Social Workers Aspiration in North Maharashtra Region

The professional social workers across all colleges and department are the human resource for social change. The regular meetings, students work shops and seminar across all

these institutions along with the primary data enforced to study aspiration of specialized social work students as given in table :1. The available specialization for social work education in NMU affiliated institutions are basically Community Development, Urban and Rural Community Development, Personnel Management and Industrial Relation and Family and Child Welfare. The student social worker are mostly following categories of aspiration to study social work education such as due to less marks at graduation level or less admission fees or need training to make career in politics or work on social issues and problems for social development or getting Govt. Job.

Table:1 Aspiration of Specialized Social Work Students

MSW Specialization	Aspiration of Social Work Students					Total	Total Cumulative Percentage
	Less marks to get admission in any other course	Expected to work in Govt. Jobs	Interested to resolve social issues and problems	Interested to enter in politics	Low Economic Fees		
Community Development	0	76	84	10	10	180	60%
<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>	0%	42%	47%	6%	6%	100%	
Personnel Management and Industrial Relation	0	18	28	4	0	50	16%
<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>	0%	36%	56%	8%	0%	100%	
Family and Child Welfare	5	30	10	7	0	52	17%
<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>	10%	58%	19%	13%	0%	100%	
Urban and Rural Community Development	0	10	6	0	6	22	7%
<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>	0%	45%	27%	0%	27%	100%	
Total	5	134	128	19	16	304	100%
<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>	2%	44%	42%	6%	5%	100%	

$X=39.010$ $df=12$ $n=304$ $P < 0.05$

Source: Primary Field Data of Ph.D. study

As per the factual data given in table: 1 specialization of community development is opted by maximum i.e 60% of total students followed by Family Child Welfare and Personnel Management and Industrial Relation i.e. 17% and 16% respectively. The 47% students with specialization of community development and 56% students with

specialization of Personnel Management and Industrial Relation were aspirant to resolve social issues and problems. On the contrary 58% students with specialization of family and child welfare and 48% of Urban and rural community Development students were aspirant of Gov. Jobs.

The chi square table value is 39.010 where degree of freedom is 12 and significance value i.e. p is less than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis rejected. There is a significant relationship between specialization of social work education and aspirations of social work educators.

Hence it is strongly observed that the students with specialization of community development are having strong aspiration to work for social development i.e. to resolve social issues and problems. It is also followed by the aspiration of government jobs by student social workers.

Conclusion:

Social work education is with vision to create human resource for social development by resolving issues and problems of society. The factual research finding in north Maharashtra region about profession social workers are really optimistic and inline with vision of social work education. The most students social workers are interested to address social issues and address social problems. The students are believing that the issues and problems will be resolved by working within system or outside the system. Hence there are no. of students interested to work in Govt. jobs. This research brings an opportunity to study aspirations of students in structural social work perspective.

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